

The Persisting Shadows of Oppression

Unveiling Contemporary Manifestations of 18th-Century Declarations

ELIKA JIREHL C. RILLERA
7-1-2022

This paper foregrounds the homogeneity of 18th-century declarations, accentuating the 1776 Declaration of Independence, which seeks emancipation from the oppressive British Crown. The declaration operated on the principle that colonies should uphold independence and not be bound by coercive acts that hegemonize its people and limit the economy. Oppression by the British Crown towards its colonies was evident particularly in taxation.¹ However, while the imperial taxation was oppressive, they united the 13 American colonies. With this came an uprising with the goal to liberate from tyranny and demand independence.²

Rights and liberation are central to the declarations authored in the 18th-century. They stood for the people and contested the oppressive framework of the government and society. The declarations banked on conservatism and progressivism in a way that they do not only challenge the government but also seek to acknowledge the responsibility of every citizen in the realization of goals—this is particularly evinced in The Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen in 1789.³ However, prior to the 1789 declaration was the Imperial Crisis that engendered the 1776 unanimous Declaration of Independence.⁴

The chronology of declarations addressed the circumstances of their society. However, each declaration incited new challenges evident with the 1789 Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen and 1791 The Rights of Women. To preempt, the 1789 declaration does aim to trivialize women, but with “man” as the dominant narrative and with the entrenched patriarchal society, it subordinated women hence the forming of Marie-Olympe de Gouges’s The Right of Women. Through these events, we evaluate the progressive nature of contemporary society and how declarations formalized and added gravity to events that shaped emergent societies.

Furthermore, recapitulating on the 1776 Declaration of Independence, the core argument centers on the case that society progressed but what was contested in the bygone declaration nevertheless persists. Even though colonies already liberated from Great Britain and formed independent states, they somehow emulated the coercive and oppressive nature of administration. Therefore, despite celebrating independence, they forged among them a structure that oppresses the people as tyranny still exists within governing bodies. In the modern society, this has been magnified due to right wing extremism that re-surfaced policies which are unconstitutional and anti-American. For instance, Article VI, Section 1, Clause 2 of the west

Virginia Code⁵ provides “tax exemption for the retirement benefits of certain state law enforcement employees but not for federal retirees who had comparable job duties.”⁶ Furthermore, the neglect to ratify certain bills also signal how problems of yesterday inhabit modern society. Such that, there is an absolute forsaking of reforms and bills in lieu of greed and self-interest—strongly evident with why Carbon Tax remains unacknowledged.⁷ Through all these, we realize different layers of oppression that governing bodies exact which was a problem sought against in the 1776 declaration yet still, unfortunately, manifests at present.¹

-
1. History.com Editors, “Continental Congress,” HISTORY (A&E Television Networks, September 13, 2019), <https://www.history.com/topics/american-revolution/the-continental-congress> .
 2. Farley Grubb, “Taxation in Colonial America,” *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History* 37, no. 1 (March 2009): 157–58, <https://doi.org/10.1080/03086530902757795> .
 3. National Constituent Assembly, *Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen*. Paris : Mondharre & Jean, 1789.
 4. Craig Yirush, “The imperial crisis,” in *The Oxford handbook of American Revolution*, (United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2013), 85
 5. Neil Gorsuch, “West Virginia Code § 11-21-12,” 2017. <http://www.wvlegislature.gov/wvcode/chapterentire.cfm?chap=11&art=21&ion=12>.
 6. “Table of Laws Held Unconstitutional in Whole or in Part by the Supreme Court | Resources | Constitution Annotated | Congress.gov | Library of Congress,” constitution.congress.gov, n.d., <https://constitution.congress.gov/resources/unconstitutional-laws/> .
 7. Alex Kotch, “Members of Congress Own up to \$93 Million in Fossil Fuel Stocks,” *The American Prospect*, January 10, 2020, <https://prospect.org/power/members-of-congress-own-up-to-93-million-in-fossil-fuel-stocks/> .

Bibliography

“Table of Laws Held Unconstitutional in Whole or in Part by the Supreme Court | Resources | Constitution Annotated | Congress.gov | Library of Congress,” n.d. <https://constitution.congress.gov/resources/unconstitutional-laws/>.

France. National Constituent Assembly, Author. Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen Adopted by the National Assembly during its Sessions on August 20, 21, 25 and 26, and Approved by the King . Paris: Mondharre & Jean, 1789. Image. <https://www.loc.gov/item/2021668069/>.

Gorsuch, Neil. “West Virginia Code § 11-21-12.” <http://www.wvlegislature.gov/wvcode/chapterentire.cfm?chap=11&art=21&ion=12>.

Grubb, Farley. “Taxation in Colonial America.” *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History* 37, no. 1 (March 2009): 157–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03086530902757795>.

History.com Editors. “Continental Congress.” HISTORY. A&E Television Networks, September 13, 2019. <https://www.history.com/topics/american-revolution/the-continental-congress>.

Kotch, Alex. “Members of Congress Own up to \$93 Million in Fossil Fuel Stocks.” *The American Prospect*, January 10, 2020. <https://prospect.org/power/members-of-congress-own-up-to-93-million-in-fossil-fuel-stocks/>.

Yirush, Craig B. "The imperial crisis." In *The Oxford handbook of the American Revolution*, p. 85. Oxford University Press, 2013.